

Sherdukpen Lexicon – Overview file

These files contain the data of the Sherdukpen lexicon. There are data of both Sherdukpen varieties – Rupa and Shergaon. The metadata of the files can be found in this table:

<i>file name</i>	<i>size (MB)</i>	<i>length (hh:mm:ss)</i>	<i>speaker(s)</i>	<i>location</i>	<i>year of birth/gender</i>	<i>topic</i>
Rupa DOI http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1213654						
SHER310514A	682	01:07:00	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	Word list 1 human being till 558 bird of prey
SHER310514B	266	00:26:23	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	Word list 516 serow till 240 liquor
SHER310514C	248	00:24:36	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	3 times 1 human being till 240 liquor
SHER310514D	16.4	00:01:37	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	Word list 241 milk till 483 flour
SHER310514E	340	00:33:41	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	Word list 484 cheese till 318 smooth
SHER310514F	448	00:44:26	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	Word list 319 soft till 441 neg imp
SHER310514G	159	00:15:45	Dorji Dema Thungdok	Thungre	1942/f	3 times 214 milk till 441 neg imp
SHER310514C+G.zip	94					all triple repeated sound files of SHER310514C and SHER310514G
SHER310514.pdf						transcribed word list
SHER010614A	547	00:56:54	Rincin Khandru Karma	Rupa	1947/m	List Dondrup depth till salt not in village
SHER010614B	680	01:07:27	Rincin Khandru Karma	Rupa	1947/m	List Dondrup woollen cloth till cover
SHER010614C	956	01:34:44	Rincin Khandru Karma	Rupa	1947/m	Complete wordlist
SHER010614D	478	00:47:27	Rincin Khandru Karma	Rupa	1947/m	3 times complete wordlist
SHER010614E	269	00:26:40	Rincin Khandru Karma	Rupa	1947/m	List Dondrup cross till next year
SHER010614ABE.zip	190					all lexemes from list Dondrup SHER010614A + B + E
SHER010614ABE.pdf						transcribed lexemes from list Dondrup SHER010614A + B + E
SHER010614D.zip	152					all cut sound files from SHER010614D

SHER010614D.pdf						transcribed word list from SHER010614C+D
SHER060215A	79	00:09:35	Tashi Sinchaji	Guwahati (Rupa)	1995(?)/m	Grammar till giving dog tomorrow
SHER060215B	1130	02:21:00	Tashi Sinchaji	Guwahati (Rupa)	1995(?)/m	Grammar complete + wordlist 3 times
SHER060215B1	239	00:43:32	Tashi Sinchaji, Yeshe Dorji Karma (Dingla), Sang Khandro Musobi (Dingla)	Guwahati (Rupa)	1995(?)/m, (?)/m, (?)/m	Wordlist 3 times
SHER060215B2	533	01:37:05	Tashi Sinchaji	Guwahati (Rupa)	1995(?)/m	Grammar
SHER060215 grammar.pdf						transcribed sentences from SHER060215A and B2
SHER060215B1.pdf						transcribed wordlist SHER060215B1
SHER060215B1.zip	87.2					all triple repeated lexemes of SHER060215B1
Shergaon DOI http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1213712						
SHER030614A	149	00:14:50	Prem Khandu Thungon	Shergaon	1940/m	Word list 1 human being till 67 liver
SHER030614B	978	01:36:56	Prem Khandu Thungon	Shergaon	1940/m	Word list 67 liver till 537 twentyfive
SHER030614C	193	00:19:10	Prem Khandu Thungon	Shergaon	1940/m	Word list 538 sixteen till 391 work
SHER030614D	148	00:14:44	Prem Khandu Thungon	Shergaon	1940/m	Word list 398 see till 441 neg imp
SHER030614E	336	00:33:23	Prem Khandu Thungon	Shergaon	1940/m	Complete wordlist three times
SHER030614.pdf						transcribed word list SHER030614A-E
SHER030614E.zip	94.8					all cut sound files word list SHER030614E